

EXTENT OF WORK VALUES MANIFESTED AND PERFORMANCE LEVEL OF TEACHERS HANDLING MULTI-GRADE PUPILS IN THE MUNICIPALITIES OF SARANGANI PROVINCE

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Abstract: This explanatory correlation study determined the extent of work values manifested and performance level of teachers handling multi-grade pupils in the municipalities of Sarangani Province during the school year 2016-2017. Data were gathered through survey questionnaire from 120 respondents chosen via stratified proportional sampling and employing Slovin's formula to determine the sample size. Data were treated with weighted average mean and Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient. A significant relationship was found between the extent of work values and performance level of respondents. The respondents often manifested their work values with a very satisfactory level of teaching performance.

Keywords: Extent of work values manifested, performance level of teachers, multi-grade pupils, Philippines.

1. INTRODUCTION

A teacher approaches his works with a distinctive attitude and with different desires towards it. The attitude he has toward the work environment has its roots in the values and experience that he brings to his work. The disposition that a teacher has toward work can influence how willingly and readily he will adjust to his work and how much fulfillment he will obtain from it. Undoubtedly, knowledge and understanding of work values among public school teachers would enhance, encourage, and facilitate understanding and solving different academic problems and issues emerging from the influence of operational values (Unos, 2017). When teachers join the school system, they bring characteristics and attributes that may influence their function's performance, either favorably or unfavorably. Teachers are next to carry out efficiently whatever accountabilities and tasks given to them. The work values which teachers bring into their workplace decide their needs, which are either physiological or psychological (Zabala & Lachica, 2018).

Certainly, values and changes in significant priorities are considered as the relevant principles to affect attrition (Santhanalakshmi, Prabhakar & Kumar, 2014) in the organization. It plays a crucial character that would portray the lives of individuals to recognize, understand, and express the individual set of values towards sound decision making (Dean, 2012). Work values are the mindfulness, affective desires, individual needs, or wants of individuals that guide their behavior towards work (Pandey & Sharma, 2012).

Moreover, the experience of effective and successful teachers has shown that the teacher's job is not concerned solely with the transmission of information and knowledge. The function of a teacher is complex and many-sided and must have a variety of work-related values and competencies. The work values of teachers spell accomplishment or dissatisfaction. Higher work values nourish morale and contribute to continuing good performance (Carteciano, 2012).

With the recent education reform, wherein the K-12 curriculum was adopted, recognizing the work-related values of teachers should be a priority in any school organization. The function of teachers can be best recognized when their behavior toward a job is considered. The work values that teachers hold when harnessed by principals, supervisors, and higher authorities can enhance satisfaction and productivity (Paez, 2013).

This study looked into the relationship between the performance of teachers handling multi-grade pupils and the work values manifested. The researcher was intrinsically motivated to embark on this study since she sought ways to improve her performance.

Statement of the Problem

The study aimed to determine the extent of work values manifested by teachers handling multi-grade pupils and their performance level in the seven (7) municipalities of Sarangani Province during the school year 2016-2017.

Specifically, it sought responses to the questions below:

1. What is the extent of work values of teachers handling multi-grade pupils?
2. What is the performance level of teachers?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the extent of work values and the performance of teachers in the seven Municipalities of Sarangani Province?

Theoretical Framework

This study viewed from the theory of Elizur and Koslowsky (2000) asserted that work values are goals that one seeks to gain to fulfill a need; they may be satisfied using more than one kind of activity and occupation. Theory of work values consists of three categories, instrumental, affective, and cognitive. Analyzing work values systematically, two basic facts of the domain have been distinguished: modality of the outcome and system performance contingency. The modality of an outcome includes various values. Instrumental values have some material return or results, inclusive of pay and benefits. These values are more salient than different values are related to Maslow's physiological/safety/security needs. Various work outcomes are of a material or instrumental nature. This class of result can describe as the material, or instrumental, in a way that they are concrete and of practical use.

Likewise, affective values cope with interpersonal relationships, which are less salient than the instrumental needs, and relate to Maslow's interpersonal need stages of belongingness, love, and esteem. Cognitive values consist of items that deal with a contribution to society, achievement, personal growth, obligation, independence, interest, and hobby and use some of the same descriptive ideas and concepts as Maslow's stages (Elizur et. al., 2000).

The behavioral management theory (Maslow, 1954) is often called the human relations movement because it addresses the human dimension of work. He created one of the most broadly recognized need theories, a theory of motivation based upon a consideration of individual needs. Maslow's hierarchy of needs support managers, visualizes employee motivation. Based on more general individual needs and encouragement, the different work values are categorized as extrinsic or security/material values like pay, security, and work environment—social or relational values like interacting with people, altruism, and contribution to society—lastly, status or power values like prestige, authority, and influence.

2. METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The explanatory correlation research design was employed, wherein the investigators used the statistical correlation test to explain and measure the degree of association or relationship between two or more variables or sets of scores. The explanatory correlation research design is a correlational design wherein the researcher is interested in two variables or more co-vary. Changes in one variable are mirrored in the other's changes. The above clarification by the experts intensifies why the correlational approach was considered as the best way to achieve the objectives of this report (Creswell, 2012).

Creswell (2012) described that a quantitative approach is employed if the researcher wanted to find out a research problem based on trends in the field or on the need to clarify why something occurs. Creswell further expressed that describing a trend defines that the research problem can be responded best by a study. The researcher sought to bring about the overall tendency of individuals' responses and note how this tendency varies among people.

Research Locale

This study was conducted in the seven (7) municipalities of Sarangani Province. A total of fifty-two (52) multi-grade schools are situated in the seven municipalities. The Municipalities of Kiamba, Maasim, Alabel, Glan, Malungon, Malapatan, and Maitum are parts of Sarangani Province, which is found in the Southern Region of Mindanao, Philippines, surrounded by adjacent areas of Provinces of South Cotabato, Sultan Kudarat, Davao Occidental, Davao del Sur, and General Santos City. The majority of the population living there belonged to Indigenous People like Blaans, Kalagans, Taga-kaulos, and T'boli.

The public elementary schools and the elementary teachers who are the respondents in this study are successfully led by school heads who are highly educated and committed to the quality education of children in the community, and the people likewise are very cooperative to work for the improvement and progress of children in the schools in general. The seven municipalities achieved their vision to educate their children with quality education.

Respondents of the Study

The respondents of the study were the public elementary teachers handling multi-grade pupils in the seven municipalities of Sarangani Province. Slovin's formula was applied to calculate the desired sample size. Using Slovin's formula, a researcher can sample the population with a desired degree and accuracy (Stephanie, 2013). Out of 171 public elementary teachers, the sample size was one hundred twenty (120), and then stratified proportional sampling was also applied.

Table 1: Distribution of Respondents

MUNICIPALITY	SCHOOL	POPULATION	PROPORTIONATE SAMPLE SIZE
ALABEL	MAHAYAG PRIMARY SCHOOL	29	20
	PACO PRIMARY SCHOOL		
	FATIMA PRIMARY SCHOOL		
	DALID ELEMENTARY SCHOOL		
	GLAMANG ELEMENTARY SCHOOL		
	TINUNGKAAN ELEMENTARY SCHOOL		
	ULO LATIAN ELEMENTARY SCHOOL		
	ULO TUBAY ELEMENTARY SCHOOL		
	LIKON PRIMARY SCHOOL		
GLAN	MACATIMBOL ELEMENTARY SCHOOL	29	20
	MALATABON ELEMENTARY SCHOOL		
	SUFATUBO ELEMENTARY SCHOOL		
	CALONKAMBING ELEMENTARY SCHOOL		
	CONGAN ELEMENTARY SCHOOL		
	DLAMA ELEMENTARY SCHOOL		
	CALATUNGAN ELEMENTARY SCHOOL		
	GULO ELEMENTARY SCHOOL		
	KIAOL ELEMENTARY SCHOOL		
KIAMBA	BANATE IP SCHOOL	24	17
	BADTASAN ELEMENTARY SCHOOL		

	BOCAY –IL ELEMENTARY SCHOOL		
	CABADING ELEMENTARY SCHOOL		
	MAMANGOS MAULANA KANDOG ELEMENTARY SCHOOL		
	GASI ELEMENTARY SCHOOL		
	KAPANAL ELEMENTARY SCHOOL		
	TAMANDANG ELEMENTARY SCHOOL		
MAASIM	CALFUNGAL PRIMARY SCHOOL	21	15
	ARCAL ELEMENTARY SCHOOL		
	CABANSAL M. LARRY IP SCHOOL		
	DATAL BASAK IP INTEGRATED SCHOOL		
	LANGARAN ELEMENTARY SCHOOL		
	CLAUDIO L. LIM IP SCHOOL		
	PANANAG ELEMENTARY SCHOOL		
MAITUM	ANGKO ELEMENTARY SCHOOL	21	15
	BATIAN ELEMENTARY SCHOOL		
	KIAYAP ELEMENTARY SCHOOL		
	PINOL ELEMENTARY SCHOOL		
	TUANADATU ELEMENTARY SCHOOL		
MALAPATAN	ALYENG IP SCHOOL	20	14
	LASANG ELEMENTARY SCHOOL		
	SITIO LANA O IP SCHOOL		
	AKBUAL IP SCHOOL		
	TUSAN IP SCHOOL		
	PITAK ELEMENTARY SCHOOL		
MALUNGON	BALITANGAN ELEMENTARY SCHOOL	27	19
	KANYUGAN ELEMENTARY SCHOOL		
	KIDENGEN IP SCHOOL		
	OSMEÑA ELEMENTARY SCHOOL		
	DATU MANANGKA MATANGGO ELEMENTARY SCHOOL		
	JWB ADORACION ELEMENTARY SCHOOL		
	TANDAWANAN INTEGRATED SCHOOL		
	FYE FALEL IP SCHOOL		
TOTAL		171	N=120

Sampling Procedure

The respondents of the study were the 120 public elementary teachers handling multi-grade pupils in the seven Municipalities of Sarangani Province. Slovin's formula has applied, followed by stratified proportional sampling was used to get the final sample of the respondents.

Instrumentation

The data gathering tools applied in this study was in the form of a survey questionnaires which are the questionnaire on the job values of public elementary teachers managing multi-grade students and the Public Teachers' Individual Performance Engagement and Evaluation Form (IPCRF).

Work Values Questionnaire. This instrument is designed to gather the work values manifested by the public elementary teachers handling multi-grade classes. The questionnaire was based and adapted from Avallone, Farnese, Pepe, and Vecchione (2010). It consisted of thirty (30) different characteristics of work values.

To answer it, the respondents chose from the options provided with the choices of (5) which means that the work values of elementary teachers are always manifested;(4) often manifested;(3) sometimes are manifested;(2) seldom manifested;(1) which means that the work values of elementary teachers are never manifested; The respondents were instructed to check the box according to the column appropriate to their choice.

Individual Performance Commitment and Review Form. It refers to the instrument used to determine the individual performance of public elementary teachers. Their performance is labeled as outstanding, very satisfactory, satisfactory, fair, and poor.

Data Gathering Procedure

In conducting this research, the researcher followed the following steps:

The Procedure in Asking Permission to Conduct the Study. Having found the research instruments valid and reliable, the researcher proceeded to ask permission and approval from the district supervisors of Municipality of Alabel. The researcher administered the instruments personally to survey the respondents.

Procedure for Getting the Data. Upon permission, the researcher administered the questionnaires personally and retrieved them immediately. The respondents assured that their answers on the questionnaires would be held confidential, and they had the option to write their names or not at all.

Data Analysis

The researcher tabulated and processed the data manually. Quantitative data processing determined the appropriate statistical tools to arrive at precise analysis and interpretation of results. The data matrix based on dummy tables was organized, summarized, and analyzed how the variables relate to each other.

Statistical Tools

The following are the statistical tools used to treat the data gathered by sub-problem:

For subproblem 1, which asked the work values of public elementary teachers handling multi-grade classes, weighted

arithmetic mean was used to treat the data gathered with the formula, $\bar{X} = \frac{\sum fx}{\sum f}$

For subproblem 2, which asked for the individual performance of public elementary teachers, the weighted arithmetic mean was also employed.

For subproblem number 3, which determined the significant relationship between the extent of work values of teachers handling multi-grade and their performance level in the seven Municipalities of Sarangani Province,

Pearson's Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (Pearson r) was applied with the formula,

$$r = \frac{n(\sum xy) - (\sum x)(\sum y)}{\sqrt{[n\sum x^2 - (\sum x)^2][n\sum y^2 - (\sum y)^2]}}$$

Where:

r= the Pearson Product Moment Coefficient of Correlation

n= sample size

$\sum xy$ = the sum of the product of x and y

$\sum x \sum y$ = the product of the sum of

$\sum x$ and the sum of $\sum y$

$\sum x^2$ = sum of squares of x

$\sum y^2$ = sum of squares of y

3. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSIONS

The Extent of Work Values Manifested by Teachers Handling Multi-grade Pupils in the Municipalities of Sarangani Province

This study intended to determine the extent of work values manifested by teachers handling multi-grade pupils in the Municipalities of Sarangani Province. As shown in Table 2, the multi-grade teachers' often manifest their work values.

This implies that, the work values of teachers handling multi-grade pupils most of the time manifest to assume a leadership position and have decision making authority, get ahead in the working world and succeed more than others, to have ambition and be career-oriented, to organize others work, being attentive to colleagues' needs and emotional states, respect colleagues' work and make an effort to understand their point of view even if they do not share it, dedicate attention to and listen to colleagues when they do not esteem very much, and to be open to forgive a colleague who acted up towards them.

Also, teachers often expressed loyalty to colleagues doing several things and using the customs learned, respecting customs rather than sharing their ideas, avoiding expressing one's thoughts if their supervisor or colleagues might challenge them, not contradicting their head or older colleagues, working while staying loyal to practices and without adhering to ongoing reforms, and having invigorated their head or older colleagues.

Moreover, teachers often manifested to be interested in their work, become curious and attempt to understand every situation, learn different aspects of their work and acquire new competencies, propose new ideas and express individual's creativity within the workplace, seek out challenging objectives at work, select a job which consents one to enjoy their lives, find pleasant and entertaining occasions within the workplace, have a guaranteed and stable work position, work for an organization where employees rights are protected, recognize that on the workplace, safety norms and regulations concerning the prevention of accidents are followed.

Furthermore, the teachers' work values sometimes manifested to be the person-in-charge and tell others what to do, and to adapt oneself to organizational requests even if they go against their principal.

In summary, the average mean of work values of teachers is ($\bar{x} = 4.10$), which is often manifested. This implies that teachers handling multi-grade pupils most of the time manifested their work values in their work place.

These findings are further supported by Henard et. al., (2012) who state that teachers serve as role model of the behavior of favorable disposition that leads the learner towards a fruitful direction and college life occasions. Keeping up and demonstrating positive work attitudes among teachers would also give a clear picture of a living example of the real attributes of professionalism and integrity. The delivery of the lessons by teachers and how they supervise classroom settings could lead to students' satisfaction with learning and development. It is evaluated periodically to gather some data and information that would serve as the basis for continuous improvement of the institution.

Further, Somblingo (2014) asserted that teachers are expected to demonstrate appropriate values and virtues in life. One dimension that focused on teachers' values as role models is the social regard for learning. Teachers with values and acts as role models contribute to the positive development of human resources, then rooted in favorable relationships.

Table 2: The Extent of Work Values Manifested Among Multi-grade Teachers

Indicators	Mean	Description
Work Values		
1. To assume a leadership position and have decision making authority.	3.83	Often manifested
2. Being the person in charge and telling others what to do.	3.47	Sometimes manifested
3. Getting ahead in the working world and succeeding more than others.	3.67	Often manifested
4. To have ambition and be career-oriented.	4.34	Often manifested
5. To organize others' work.	4.00	Often manifested
6. To be successful at work.	4.92	Always manifested
7. Being attentive to colleagues' needs and emotional states.	3.89	Often manifested
8. Respecting colleagues' work and make an effort to understand their point of view even if he/she does not share it.	4.41	Often manifested
9. Dedicating attention to and listening to colleagues' he/she does not esteem very much.	3.90	Often manifested

10. Being available when colleagues require his/her help	4.53	Always manifested
11. Being open to forgive a colleague who acted improperly towards him/her.	4.06	Often manifested
12. To be loyal to colleagues.	3.94	Often manifested
13. Doing many things and using the customs learned.	4.02	Often manifested
14. Respecting customs, rather than expressing his/her ideas.	4.23	Often manifested
15. Avoid expressing one's ideas if his/her boss or colleagues might criticize them.	3.73	Often manifested
16. Adapting oneself to organizational requests, even if they go against his/her principal.	3.48	Sometimes manifested
17. Not contradicting his/her head or older colleagues.	3.89	Often manifested
18. Working while remaining loyal to traditions and without adhering to continuous changes.	3.71	Often manifested
19. Stimulating work activities, even if unexpected organizational changes are involved.	4.07	Often manifested
20. Recognizing how to manage repetitive changes at work.	4.25	Often manifested
21. Being interested in his/her work, being curious, and attempting to understand every situation.	4.25	Often manifested
22. Learning different aspects of his/her work and acquiring new competencies.	4.43	Often manifested
23. Proposing new ideas and expressing one's creativity within the workplace.	4.19	Often manifested
24. To seek out challenging objectives at work.	4.06	Often manifested
25. To select a job, this consents one to enjoy his/her life.	3.89	Often manifested
26. Having a job that is fun and making him/her feel good.	4.53	Always manifested
27. Finding pleasant and entertaining occasions within the workplace	4.18	Often manifested
28. Having a guaranteed and stable work position	4.48	Often manifested
29. Working for an organization where employees' rights are protected.	4.48	Often manifested
30. Recognizing that on the job site, safety norms and regulations concerning the prevention of accidents followed.	4.18	Often manifested
Overall Mean	4.10	Often manifested

Performance Level of Teachers

This study also determined the performance level of teachers handling multi-grade pupils in the Municipalities of Sarangani Province. Table 3 shows the result based on their performance commitment and review (IPCRF) rating.

As shown in Table 3, the teaching-learning process had achieved an outstanding level in preparing daily lesson logs/plans activities, including appropriate, adequate, and updated instructional materials. Also, they were very satisfactory in initiating discipline of pupils including classroom rules and guidelines in accomplishing individual/group task throughout RPMS cycle and facilitating learning in the classroom through functional daily lesson logs/plans and innovative teaching strategies and

In terms of the pupils/students outcome, they had a very satisfactory level of performance in conducting remediation/enrichment program to improve the class performance indicators, attaining the 75% level of achievement per subject area and evaluating pupils/students' progress every rating period with analysis.

In terms of community involvement, they also had a very satisfactory level of performance in conducting regular/periodic homeroom PTA meetings/conferences following the reduced Class Friday Program, undertaking/initiating projects/activities sponsored by the parents and other community stakeholders within the RPMS cycle, and visiting parents of pupils/students needing academic monitoring to follow up within the RPMS cycle.

In terms of professional growth, it showed that they had an outstanding level of performance in participating/attending division/district and school activities such as Teachers' Day Celebration, Independence Day, Team Building, and others; also, they had a very satisfactory level of performance in pursuing post-graduate and graduate studies, and publishing publication, creating works for province/division/school circulation for at least once every quarter throughout the RPMS Cycle.

In summary, the average mean on the level of performance of teachers based on their individual's performance commitment and review form is 4.19, described as a very satisfactory level implies that teachers handling multi-grade pupils, had performances that exceeded expectations and achieved all goals, objectives, and targets above established standards.

In the studies conducted by Bakar et. al., (2012) they state that work values might be considered a factor in deciding the work performance of teachers. Work values revealed foresee career preferences in different organizations, and the similarity of work values with the workplace had appeared to exist. Dramatic changes also occur in the work environment due to globalization, the advancement of technology, and a borderless world.

**Table 3: Level of Performance of Teachers Handling Multi-grade Pupils Individual's Performance Commitment and Review Form
SY 2016-2017**

Key Result Areas	Objectives	Mean	Adjectival Rating
Teaching-learning Process (40%)	a. Prepared Daily Lesson Logs/plans activities including appropriate, adequate, and updated instructional materials	4.61	Outstanding
	b. Facilitated learning in the classroom through functional daily lesson logs/plans and innovative teaching strategies	4.31	Very Satisfactory
	c. The initiated discipline of pupils, including classroom rules and guidelines in accomplishing individual/group task throughout the RPMS cycle	4.13	Very Satisfactory
Pupils/ Students Outcome (20%)	a. Evaluated Pupils/students' progress every rating period with analysis	4.27	Very Satisfactory
	b. Conducted a remediation/enrichment program to improve the class performance indicators	4.16	Very Satisfactory
	c. Attained the 75% level of achievement per subject area	4.34	Very Satisfactory
Community Involvement (30%)	a. Conducted regular/periodic Homeroom PTA meetings/conferences following the Reduced Class Friday Program	4.12	Very Satisfactory
	b. Visited parents of pupils/students needing academic monitoring to follow up within the RPMS cycle	4.16	Very Satisfactory
	c. Undertaken/initiated projects/activities sponsored by the parents and other community stakeholders within the RPMS cycle	4.09	Very Satisfactory
	a. Pursued Post Graduate and Graduate Studies	3.81	Very Satisfactory

Professional Growth (10%)	b. Published Publication, created works for Provincial/Division/School circulation for at least once every quarter throughout the RPMS Cycle	3.66	Very Satisfactory
	c. Participated/Attended Division/District and school activities such as Teachers' Day Celebration, Independence Day, Team Building, and Others	4.56	Outstanding
Overall Mean		4.19	Very Satisfactory

The Relationship between the Extent of Work Values of teachers Handling Multi-grade pupils and their Level of Performance

To determine whether the extent of work values are significantly related to the level of performance of teachers handling multi-grade pupils, Pearson's Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (Pearson r) was employed.

As shown in Table 4, the correlation results showed that the performance of the teachers is significantly related to their extent of work values. Since the computed value of r, which is 0.46, is greater than the tabular value of r, which is 0.1946 at a .05 (2-tailed) level of significance, these results led to the rejection of the null hypothesis that there is a significant relationship between the extent of work values of teachers handling multi-grade pupils and their performance level in the municipalities of Sarangani Province.

It means that teachers performed better if they had work values. On the other hand, if teachers are promoted to a higher position, their performance as a teacher is a good indicator of how much they value their work.

The findings of the study affirm the theory of Elizur and Koslowsky (2000); who asserted that work values like awareness, affective desires, and individual needs or wants of people guide their behavior towards work. It creates a set of objectives for an individual to look for an environment that plays a crucial part in professional growth and career improvement. It is the satisfying results that individuals anticipate or can obtain through their engagement, interest, and constructive participation in work exercises that further drive individuals' motivation to accomplish specific tasks and contribute to achieving an organization's vision and purpose.

The findings of the study also affirm the idea of Lovat (2005) that work values have the potential to stimulate practicing teachers' reflections about the values and goals they communicate in their classroom. Such self-knowledge and self-management are characteristics thought to be central to quality teaching. It could help teachers design learning environments that maximize students' achievement motivation through the conscious endorsement of values that link to productive goals and goals which link to beneficial values.

Table 4: The Relationship between the Extent of Work Values Manifested by Teachers Handling Multi-grade Pupils and their Level of Performance

Variables	df	r		p-value	Decision at .05 level	Remarks
		Computed	Tabular			
The Extent of Work Values of Teachers Vs Performance of Public Elementary Teachers	118	.46	.1946	.000	Reject the null hypothesis	Significant

4. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions are made:

1. The work values of teachers handling multi-grade pupils are often manifested.
2. Teachers handling multi-grade pupils have a very satisfactory teaching performance.
3. There is a significant relationship between the extent of work values of teachers handling multi-grade pupils and their level of performance.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions of the study, the preceding recommendations are given:

1. The teachers need more advance training on work values on how to quickly adapt to organizational requests to highly value and maintain the quality of work in the department.
2. Encourage teachers to attend a workshop on publishing publications and creative works at the province, division, or school level to improve their performance.
3. DepEd Officials may develop programs and interventions to help teachers to address in coping their work values and attitudes.
4. Further studies on the relationship of the extent of work values and performance of teachers handling multi-grade pupils may be conducted utilizing more respondents.

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